

Trusted CI Ship Site Visit: [Add Ship Name]

Distribution: Release to [Ship, Project Name]

Overview

Purpose: Provide a brief description of the ship and the purpose of the visit.

Date(s): What date(s) the visit occurred

Trusted CI personnel: People involved

Activity goals: Goal(s) of the activity.

External contacts: Names and affiliations/titles of any collaborators outside of the Trusted CI team

Deliverables: Link any additional deliverables produced from this visit

Important Links: List any relevant links to the vessel or the project affiliated with the ship.

[ADD GUIDANCE STATEMENT] - Explain utility for NSF inspection, in-serv inspection?

Network

- Request a walk through of their logical network diagram.
 - Is network segmentation used?
 - Are the network segments based on security requirements, data/system criticality, or other?
 - Are there connections allowed between network segments?
 - Are connections between network segments controlled by firewalls, router ACLs, or other?
- Is there a common use/BYOD network?
 - Is it available via wired, wireless, both?
 - Is access to it controlled (captive portal, etc)?
- Physical security of network infrastructure:
 - What parts of the network infrastructure have physical access controls around them?
 - Who has access?
 - Are there interlocks, or other access detection that alert / log?
- Manufacturer of networking gear (FortiNet, Cisco, etc)?
 - Are there support contracts with the manufacturer or another vendor for any of these devices?
- What Internet service providers are used (StarLink/Shield, FleetExpress, cell modem, etc)?
- What controls which Internet service is used at any given time?
 - How is it determined which Internet service to use (only availability by some like a link status, or quality of the link checks are done like connection tests to preselected destinations, etc)?
- What is the route of traffic off the ship / shore to ship (tunneled to parent org's network / directly to ISP / etc)?
- Are there network based security controls (network monitoring, IDS/IPS, honeypots, etc)?

[Insert Distribution Statement]

Facility Infrastructure

- What are the services provided for crew?
- What are the services provided for ship operations?
- What are the services provided for science parties?
- What type of virtualization / hypervisor used?
- Camera systems in use and purpose?
- Physical controls around ship systems?
- What data acquisition systems are available?
 - Are they only for ship provided sensors, or can science parties send data to them too?
- Are there backup (data / configuration / full system backup) systems for ship's systems?
 - Immutable backups of systems?
 - Immutable backups of essential research data?
- Are there redundant systems, if so which systems?
- What OS'es are used and their version?
- Is anti-virus software used?
- Are types of end-point protection (EDR/XDR software used)?
- Are system logs monitored (on-host, off-host, etc)?
 - Collect and monitor all system logs?
 - Collect and monitor all user endpoint logs?
- Are common/shared accounts used?
- Are individual accounts used?
- Is an identity management system used?
- Are admin / root accounts used?
 - Are privileged accounts used for daily tasks, or only when needed?
- Are any systems auto-logged in?
- Is MFA utilized?
 - Is MFA utilized for local or remote access?
 - Is MFA utilized for all privileged/administrator accounts?
 - Is MFA utilized for VPN from shore to ship?
- Is there any vulnerability management processes?
 - Defined process for identifying, tracking, and remediating vulnerabilities
- Is there any network or host scanning done?
- Is there any system configuration management / monitoring done?
- Is there a change management procedure?
- Are there systems build to a standard?
- Are systems hardened to a baseline control set?

Science Party Onboarding

- General description of onboarding.
- Is secure awareness training included?
- Is incident reporting included?
- Is there an acceptable use policy covered?
- Is there a process to review network connected hardware?
- Is there a process to review and agree to running a visiting scientist VM on ships hypervisor?
- Is there a process to review and agree to running a visiting scientist hardware?

[Insert Distribution Statement]

- Will the hardware be connected to a network, or data storage?
- Is data / system classification discussed (data collected is sensitive or restricted, or the science party systems are restricted or considered controlled)?

Critical Ship's Systems

- What are these systems?
- Do you maintain and update an inventory of critical infrastructure?
- What are the cyber-security controls for them?
- What are the physical controls around them?
- How do vendors get access (remote / in-person)?
- How are they updated (configuration / firmware)?
- What are the vendors of the critical systems?
- Do you have any vendor supplied hardware (example: laptop) for specific tasks or remote support?
 - How is the hardware updated/patched so it is protected when it may be necessary to utilize?

Security Procedures

- Are backups tested?
 - How frequently are backup tests exercised? (integrity/restoration)
- Are power systems (APC / UPS) monitored and tested?
- Are there Incident Response policy / procedures?
- Are security exercises regularly performed?
- What support does parent org provide for CI/CS?
- What is the relationship with parent org IT and cybersecurity teams?

Final Thoughts

Has this visit produced any recoverables for Trusted CI and/or the NSF community (e.g., new tools, processes, templates, educational materials)?

What could we do better in terms of planning and executing this and similar activities?

Any big picture, high-level observations?

Are there specific questions/issues that we should address with a follow-up meeting or engagement?

[Insert Distribution Statement]